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of **EXPRESSION**
A Creative Folio

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Between Sessions

When the door closes,
their stories linger.
I hear them in the chair,
feel them in the air.

A girl afraid to go home,
her notebook trembling.
A boy with fists
that soften into tears.

Mothers ask for strength,
fathers for patience.
Students ask only
to be understood.

I breathe in quietly,
steadying my heart.
Guidance is heavy,
but silence is heavier.

Notes fill the pages,
but not the whole truth.
What heals is presence,
not paper alone.

So I wait for the knock,
again and again.
Each story reshapes me,
each ending is still open.